

TEACHING AIDS TO TRAIN STUDENTS' TRANSLATOR COMPETENCE

Diana APOSTOL ¹

¹ University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Abstract

A 2025 EU Commission Science Hub survey reports on the substantial influence digitalization has brought to the workforce, revealing that 90% of employees across the European Union routinely use computers, mobile devices, and office software in their professional activities. Furthermore, 30% have adopted Artificial Intelligence tools, particularly for tasks involving text generation and translation. In response to the rapidly evolving modern landscape, higher education institutions are increasingly incorporating digital tools into their curricula. With a view to the contemporary trends on inclusivity and diversity to secure cultural sustainability, we look on the use of computer-assisted research tools and web-based resources that facilitate the investigation of digital corpora

in an attempt to develop and strengthen our students' multifaceted translator competence. Building on prior tutorials and the capabilities of MAXQDA 24.10 - dedicated software for data import, transcription, and analysis, we guide our students in a translation-oriented investigation of multimodal content. Resorting to CAT tools, our graduates build-up specific skills relevant to Corpus-Based Translation Studies, with particular emphasis on both qualitative and quantitative analysis methods and employ Visual Tools to generate comprehensive result diagrams. Our trial is designed to familiarize graduate students with technological skills relevant to the changing labour market in the field of Translation and Interpretation and introduce some interactive components focused on digital humanities.

Keywords: computer-assisted tools, Corpus-Based Translation Studies, digital corpora, multimodal pedagogy, reflective learning, translator competence.

1. Introduction

In today's interconnected media landscape effective translation remains essential not only for supporting global communication, but also for safeguarding cultural identities.

The translation industry is undergoing rapid transformation, propelled by technological advancements that are reshaping both professional practice and educational paradigms. As a result, translators are now expected to possess a blend of linguistic proficiency and technological expertise to meet the evolving demands of the industry.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and qualitative analysis platforms have emerged as pivotal tools, fostering richer learning experiences and improving how feedback is provided in translator training. Such technologies create adaptable and dynamic training environments that support the development of responsive and effective educational settings. The present paper addresses the

didactic contribution of corpus-based translation applications, focusing on a computer-assisted analysis model of a multimodal corpus. Resorting to MAXQDA 24.10 analysis software, graduate students were challenged to design and analyse four authentic MP4 multimedia sub-corpora, i.e. four travel guides promoted by an international travel technology company. At each stage of our training project we monitored our trainees' involvement, interaction, and responsiveness to AI tools and corpus-based tasks.

Our research focused on identifying significant patterns in the translation difficulties faced by our students. Such findings may inform corrective training strategies and ultimately guide future syllabi revisions.

In what follows we outline some student training approaches to enhance language proficiency, digital literacy, and cultural awareness. A central aspect of the learning framework was to document and analyse how localization and exoticization - expressed through various modes - can influence intercultural communication and promote meaningful cultural engagement. Special emphasis was placed on strategic elements such as colour symbolism, sound branding, and narrative voice, to increase students' awareness on a balanced perspective between global accessibility and the authenticity of local cultures. By systematically integrating multimodal strategies into translation, our students develop enhanced competencies that facilitate effective language bridging and promote intercultural communication.

2. Contemporary Translator Training Perspectives

The theoretical foundations of Translation Studies and Multimodality underpin the development of the contemporary translator's complex skill profile, guiding our pedagogical approaches in translator education.

2.1. Translation Studies and Multimodality

A solid understanding of key theoretical principles in translation studies is essential for the effective preparation of contemporary translators, securing the basic framework required to address the challenging issues in translation practice.

Over time, several influential models have shaped the pedagogical landscape in this field. Notably, the Skopos Theory put forward by Hans J. Vermeer (1978) advanced the functionalist approach, emphasizing that translation strategies should be guided by the intended purpose - or skopos - of the target text (TT) within its cultural context. Building on this foundation, Venuti's (1995) concepts of domestication and foreignization address the enduring tension between adapting content for target audiences (domestication) and preserving the cultural uniqueness of the source text (foreignization). Such approaches highlight the ethical and cultural considerations that translators must balance when mediating between source and target cultures.

Expanding the scope of translation studies beyond textual elements, Kress and van Leeuwen focus in *Reading Images* (2000) on the interplay of visual, verbal, and auditory modes in meaning-making. Hence, the two authors embarked on investigating how different modes - such as text, image, and sound - convey ecological and cultural narratives, further emphasizing the significance of multimodality in contemporary communication. In a similar vein, Kaindl's concept of multimodal translatability (1999) explores the challenges associated with adapting non-verbal cues, such as gestures and music, in translation. The perspective adopted by Kaindl (*ibid*) highlights the challenge of translating multimodal texts and the need for specialised strategies to preserve meaning across different modes. Taking a step further, Baker's *Narrative Theory* (2006) explores the ways stories are built and reshaped through translation, bringing narrative analysis into the field of Translation Studies. This perspective sheds

light on how translators impact meaning, since their choices in storytelling can affect how cultures are viewed.

We concur that, collectively, these models demonstrate significant advancements in Translation Studies. The discipline has broadened its scope beyond function and ethics to include multimodality, relevance, and narrative, all of which are essential components of effective intercultural communication.

2.2. Contemporary Pedagogical Insights and Digital Methodologies

Contemporary advances in both pedagogy and digital technology have reshaped translator training programs to accommodate dynamic and more responsive educational environments. In line with some current research studies, we highlight the influence of the constructivist and active learning paradigms to have influenced this shift. Social constructivism, as articulated by Vygotsky (1978), and discovery learning, advanced by Bruner (1996), emphasize the importance of active learner-centered approaches that promote knowledge acquisition via authentic tasks, collaboration, and reflective practice. In the same spirit, Hattie (2009) underlines the critical role of feedback and formative assessment in fostering effective learning outcomes.

As the journey unfolds, we find translator education at the cusp of a tech-driven ‘renaissance’. Today AI-powered platforms enable the personalization of translation tasks, supporting adaptive learning and differentiated instruction, tailored to individual student needs (Heffernan and Heffernan, 2014; Holmes et al., 2019). Additionally, the incorporation of gamification strategies (Deterding et al., 2011) and peer instruction models (Mazur, 1997, 2013) has been proven to enhance student engagement and promote collaborative learning. The connectivist framework, as put forward by Siemens (2005) and Downes (2012), further posits that learning occurs across networks, with technology facilitating meaningful connections and the sharing of knowledge.

Equally significant is the emergence of multimodal and multiliteracies pedagogy. The New London Group (1996) and Kalantzis and Cope (2012) advocate for the integration of multiple modes - visual, audio, and textual - within educational practice, reflecting the diverse communicative demands of the contemporary society. Gee (2003, 2007) explores the development of digital literacies and the pivotal role of interactive media in learning. In parallel, Wiliam (2011) and Tomlinson (2014) emphasize the importance of differentiated instruction and formative assessment, ensuring that teaching remains inclusive and responsive to the varied needs of learners.

Recent empirical studies highlight the growing significance and impact of multimodal pedagogy across higher education and translator training. For example, Guo et al. (2024) conducted a comprehensive bibliometric and content analysis of multimodal teaching research from 1995 to 2023, revealing a marked increase in scholarly output and a shift toward technology-enhanced, multimodal learning environments. Their findings focus on key themes such as multimedia human-computer interaction that reflect the expanding role of digital tools in facilitating multimodal instruction. Also, Argyriou and Tapsis (2025) examined some main contemporary research trends in multimodal education, highlighting the shift from digital learning to a broader social semiotic pedagogical framework. Their work advocates for multimodal pedagogies that foster learner agency, inclusivity, and critical literacy, particularly through project-based and collaborative digital activities.

In the context of translator education, Hou (2024) explores the application of multimodality in translation teaching, demonstrating that the use of images, audio, video, and other media materials helps students grasp the cultural context of source texts and cultivates cross-cultural communication skills. Project-based learning, such as subtitle translation and game localization, is shown to enhance

practical abilities and innovative thinking among translation students. Recent studies also point to the motivational benefits of multimodal pedagogy. Bashir et al. (2025) found that computer-assisted multimodal resources significantly increase learner motivation and willingness to communicate in a second language, both inside and outside the classroom.

To put in a nutshell, the theoretical insights provided above advocate that multimodal pedagogy not only enriches instructional content and fosters engagement, but also supports inclusivity, critical literacy, and the development of essential skills for the digital age.

3. Teaching Approaches in Multimodal Translator Training

Blending theoretical frameworks with modern teaching methods is crucial to improving translator education. By combining classic theories and new teaching strategies, students develop skills that are vital in today's global, tech-driven world.

3.1. Research Question and Training Design

The integration of key theoretical frameworks, such as Skopos Theory, domestication and foreignization, and multimodal analysis into modern pedagogical approaches has proven to bring considerable added value to the development of the multifaceted translators' competence within the context of an increasingly globalized and technologically driven landscape. However, the extent to which these frameworks can be operationalized to foster strategic and technological competences in translation students remains an open empirical question.

Under the circumstances, we set out to find out to what extent a computer-assisted translation project simulation could enhance students' translation competence, with an emphasis on strategic and technological skills. To investigate this question, we designed a pedagogical framework centred on the

analysis of a digital MP4 corpus of four authentic travel guides. The framework emphasises the analysis of language-related and multimodal features that highlight cultural elements, adopting a translation-oriented perspective to evaluate the effectiveness of visual and auditory communication in cross-cultural exchanges. Special attention is paid to the contemporary strategies of localization and exoticization, rooted in Venuti's (1995) concepts of domestication and foreignization, to explore how these approaches facilitate intercultural understanding and authentic cultural engagement among viewers.

Our research approach has several limitations to consider as well. On the one hand, our training simulation is constrained by the representativeness of the selected corpus, which may not encompass the full spectrum of linguistic and cultural complexities encountered in professional translation practice. On the other hand, the findings are context-dependent, shaped by the specific cohort of second year master's students and the instructional environment in which the study is conducted.

Despite these limitations, our objective is to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the integration of theory and practice in translator education, with particular emphasis on the opportunities and challenges presented by computer-assisted, multimodal training methods.

3.2. Instructional Strategies and Methodologies

Adapting the analysis framework put forward by Kruger et al. (2011), we resorted corpus-based investigations and comparative reviews to examine how effectively such training methods enhance students' strategic and technological skills. To design and develop our corpus-based analysis project we used the previously mentioned dedicated software - MAXQDA 24.10.

As far as the instructional approach is concerned, we applied a flipped classroom model, engaging students with translation cases through digital tools

before class sessions, thus encouraging active participation and facilitating deeper learning. Based on Laviosa's (2010: 6) translation training approach, we created a translation project to foster interactive, collaborative skill-building that meets current market demands.

The translation project and our parallel monitoring of students' performance - via qualitative and quantitative corpus-based methods - envisage not only the immediate development of translation competence and trainee autonomy, but also the drafting and development of sustainable translation digital resources such as thematic maps and workbenches.

3.3. Corpus Desing and Analytical Procedures

During the first three stages of our trial, 2nd year students enrolled in the translation training master's program were organised in three teams of 3 or 4 members and tasked to design a multimodal corpus by importing the four MP4 travel guides in MAXQDA 24.10.

The software provides data processing features, including automatic transcription of audio and video content. Advanced features like coding options allowed students to conduct qualitative and quantitative analysis of the multimodal corpus using colour-based labels. At this stage, focusing on both semantic and cultural aspects, students are encouraged to identify and encode translation choices in terms of translation strategies, language patterns and cultural references. Thus, relevant segments are identified and thematically encoded (e.g., "Food Reference," "Humour/Idiom," "Cultural Load"). Applying a pre-established analysis model, students focus on the multimodal and translation-oriented research parameters to record diverse communication modes.

Localization and exoticization strategies are examined across visual, auditory, and narrative elements to balance global and local appeal. Strategic

tools such as colour symbolism, sound branding, and narrative voice are approached to feature cross-cultural communication. During this phase, colour coding is implemented to facilitate efficient visual identification, while colour-based labels such as “exoticization” and “localization” are assigned to enhance clarity.

The third stage challenges students with data visualization. Following the processing and analysis of the multimodal content, students select various data visualization features provided by the software to better identify and illustrate patterns and trends by means of document portraits and word clouds. Adopting this strategy, we guide students in developing a systematic approach to analyse how multimodal translation strategies address linguistic gaps and enhance communication effectiveness.

3.4. Performance Monitoring and Reflective Learning

To equip students with digital and strategic skills aligned with current translation industry demands, we integrated parallel progress monitoring and regular debriefings into our computer-assisted analysis.

As far as the translation process and product are concerned, we sought to train our students via button-up practice activities. We used both quantitative and qualitative methods in our investigation. Assigning both individual and team-based tasks, we aimed at establishing the nature and the incidence rate of most frequently encountered difficulties in terms of language choices, the transfer of culture-related items and the appropriateness of translation strategies.

Resorting to the same dedicated software, but this time adopting the perspective of instructors, we systematically tracked students’ concern and involvement throughout all the stages of the project. Our objective was to document both qualitatively and quantitatively our students’ responsiveness to computer-assisted corpus-based investigations and the integration of AI tools.

After each project stage, we imported students' corpus analysis reports and findings into MAXQDA 24.10. The imported corpus was then encoded according to some main training-oriented objectives previously set. Thus, we carried out both quantitative and qualitative analyses on the adequacy of the identified translation procedures (encoded with red), language difficulties, i.e. lexical issues (green), syntactic problems (orange), cultural transfer (purple), etc. Using this colour-based comparison method, we further selected the Visual Tools feature from the main menu. The software generates a coded document overview that illustrates how often our students experienced difficulties during the analysis. The quantitative analysis was further developed via a distribution chart to show the relationship between the codes and the predefined variables. As shown in Figure 1, the Code-Matrix-Browser option displays a diagram of the most common analysis difficulties for each team.

Figure 1. Code distribution chart via Code-Matrix-Browser

Through parallel monitoring, we were able to spot key trends in the translation challenges students faced. These insights may allow us to optimise our training strategies to better address the typical problems that arise when analysing large multimodal corpora.

At the same time, the debriefing sessions served as a 'forum' for reflection, allowing students to evaluate outcomes, discuss their findings, and consider the effectiveness of their approaches. By reflecting on the analytical

process and its results, students were encouraged to critically assess their own understanding and application of translation strategies, fostering deeper learning and competence development.

4. Results Interpretation

Our three-phase project was designed to enhance the translation skills of second-year Master's students through the use of smart process applications and specialized software tailored for qualitative and mixed methods research. In the initial stage, an integrated translation environment was established to build strategic skills via procedural knowledge and dedicated software. Students were divided into three teams, each assigned to analyse a specific video, focusing on localization adaptation, cultural context, colour symbolism, sound branding, and narrative voice. The simulation confirmed the research hypotheses, as our computer-based translation project increased trainees' self-reliance and autonomy, while corpus-based translation tools enhanced operational skills, strategic planning, and technological competence.

Additionally, based on our simultaneous monitoring surveys conducted throughout every phase of the training project, we were able to determine that:

- computer-assisted activities enhanced students' engagement during translation training classes, more than 85% of the trainees actively participated in the project;
- all members of the three teams completed their tasks responsibly, contributing to the team's progress and meeting translation assignment requirements;
- button-up translation assignments encourage proactive collaboration and prompt responsiveness;
- 80% of team members effectively met their internal responsibilities, consistently adhering to established deadlines and quality assurance standards;

- by project end, each of the three teams achieved a completion rate ranging from 65% to 97%.

Follow-up results of our students' corpus-based investigation tasks showed that 6 out of 14 students (42,86%) struggled most with applying translation procedures, while 8 of our 14 students (57,14%) faced language-related challenges. Of the 14 students, only 3 trainees encountered frequent difficulties (more than 5 occurrences per video) when addressing the transfer of culture-related items.

5. Conclusion

The systematic integration of theoretical models and contemporary pedagogical approaches is essential for the advancement of translator education. Such approaches promote language proficiency, digital literacy, and cultural awareness by engaging students in authentic, multimodal tasks and corpus-based translation applications. Furthermore, the incorporation of AI-driven feedback and adaptive learning environments supports reflective practice, critical thinking, and collaborative learning. Through personalized guidance and real-time interaction, students are empowered to refine their translation strategies and engage meaningfully with peers and instructors.

Collectively, these pedagogical perspectives and digital strategies establish a solid framework for developing translator training programs that are both forward-thinking and responsive to the multifaceted demands of today's educational environment.

The incorporation of constructivist and active learning paradigms places students at the centre of the educational process, emphasizing authentic tasks, collaboration, and reflective practice. Social constructivism and discovery learning encourage knowledge construction through meaningful engagement and

real-world problem solving, while the critical role of feedback and formative assessment ensures that learning remains responsive and effective.

At the same time, the integration of technology transforms translator education by enabling adaptive, personalized learning experiences. AI-driven platforms, gamification strategies, and peer instruction models increase student engagement and foster collaborative learning environments. Hence, our research project facilitated via dedicated software and AI tools promote peer review, teamwork, and a deeper understanding of translation dynamics. This pedagogical approach also encourages critical thinking, self-assessment, and continuous improvement among translation students.

References

- Argyriou, M., & Tapsis, N. (2025). Reframing Multimodality in Contemporary Education: A Critical Review of Research Patterns and Pedagogical Shifts. *European Journal of Open Education and E-learning Studies*, 10 (2) , 16-32. <http://dx.doi.org/10.46827/ejoe.v10i3.6106>.
- Baker, M. (2006). *Translation and Conflict: A Narrative Account*. London: Routledge.
- Bashir, A., Aziz ,A, Imran, M., Almusharraf, N. (2025). Effect of CALL-based multimodal pedagogy on learner motivation and willingness to communicate in English: A study from university students' perspective. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 17(2), 568-586. <https://doi.org/10.30935/cedtech/15961>.
- Bruner, J. (1996). *The Culture of Education*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press.
- Deterding, S., Khaled, R., Nacke, L., Dixon, d. (2011). Gamification: Toward a definition. *CHI 2011 Gamification Workshop Proceedings*, Vancouver, 2011, 12-15.
- Gee, J. P. (2003, 2007). *What Video Games Have to Teach Us About Learning and Literacy*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Guo, X., Chen, S. & Guo, Y. (2024). Advancing multimodal teaching: a bibliometric and content analysis of trends, influences, and future directions. *Nature*. 11:1718. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-024-04254-0>
- Hattie, J. (2009). *Visible Learning*. London: Routledge.

- Heffernan, N., & Heffernan, A. (2014). The ASSISTments Ecosystem: Building a Platform that Brings Scientists and Teachers Together for Minimally Invasive Research on Human Learning and Teaching. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education* 24(4), 470-497. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s40593-014-0024-x>.
- Holmes, W., Bialik, M., & Fadel, C. (2019). *Artificial Intelligence in Education. Promise and Implications for Teaching and Learning*. Boston: Center for Curriculum Redesign.
- Hou, Y. (2024). Exploring Multimodal Approaches in Translation Teaching in the New Era. *Academic Journal of Humanities & Social Sciences*, 7(7), 103-107. doi: 10.25236/AJHSS.2024.070715.
- Kaindl, K. (1999). *Multimodality in translation*. London: Routledge.
- Kress, G., & van Leeuwen, T. (200). *Reading Images. The Grammar of Visual Design*. London: Routledge
- Kruger, A., Wallmach, K., & Munday, J. (2011). *Corpus-based translation studies: research and applications*. London and New York: Bloomsbury Academic.
- Laviosa, S. (2010). A transcultural conceptual framework for corpus-based translation pedagogy.(Keynote lecture) The International Symposium on Using Corpora in Contrastive and Translation Studies 2010 Conference (UCCTS2010), 27-29 July 2010. <https://www.lancaster.ac.uk/fass/projects/corpus/UCCTS2010Proceedings/>
- Mazur, E. (1997, 2013). *Peer Instruction*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press.
- New London Group. (1996). A Pedagogy of Multiliteracies: Designing Social Futures. *Harvard Educational Review*. 66(1), 60-92.
- Siemens, G. (2005). *Connectivism: A Learning Theory for the Digital Age*. 2. http://www.itdl.org/Journal/Jan_05/article01.htm
- Tomlinson, C. A. (2014). *The Differentiated Classroom. Responding to the Needs of all Learners*. Alexandria USA: ASCD.
- Venuti, L. (1995). *The Translator's Invisibility*. London: Routledge.
- Vermeer, H. J. (1978). Ein Rahmen für eine Allgemeine Translationstheorie. *Lebende Sprachen*. 33(3), 99–102.
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in Society*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press.
- William, D. (2011). *Embedded Formative Assessment*. Mentone: Grift Education.